

HIPPARCOS Relay Optics and IFOV Depointing Simulations (2)

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The effects of the IFOV depointing were computed with the same common parameters as given in the previous note (1982 May 25), but with the following relay optics aberrations:

Run # 6 : defocus 0.05 mm at pk, $W = 6.529E-5(y'^2 + z'^2) +$
 plus coma with max WFE = 10λ $1.804E-3(y'^2 + z'^2)y'$

The results are shown on the attached sheet, using the same graphic format as for the previous runs.

Remark: In the previous note (1982 May 25), there is a typing error in the expression for the WFE of run # 5: the correct coma coefficient is $1.804E-4$. The computations used the correct value.

Run # 6: defocus = 0.05 mm, coma = 10λ